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Large Deformation Bending Relaxation of Thin-Ply Composites Laminates

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Outline

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COLUMN BENDING TEST

LARGE DEFORMATION BENDING RELAXATION CHARACTERIZATION

VISCOELASTIC MODELING OF THIN-PLY TEXTILE LAMINATES

TEST-vs-MODEL COMPARISON

CONCLUSIONS

Background & Motivation

High Strain Composites (HSC) – Flexible polymer composites under high strains used as deployable space structures.

- Monolithic hinges
- Rollable booms
- Foldable panels / developable surfaces

Technology biggest risks:

- Deployment failure
- Loss of dimensional stability (loss of deployed shape)
- Loss of load bearing capacity

All risks are composite material relaxation/creep dependent so understanding their long-term response under high strains is crucial.

Rollable HSC booms under development at LaRC

CTM boom partially rolled

Boom axial curvature (bow) developed after a one month stowage

Boom keeps desired cross-section after curing, but flattens after prolonged stowage = 50% drop in buckling load

25 m² Solar sail deployed in the lab

Rendering of NEA Scout solar sail characterizing an asteroid

Background & Motivation

- **Thin composite laminates subjected to large bending deformations can attain significantly higher surface strains to failure than previously anticipated:**
 - Linear material model assumptions.
 - Constitutive material manufacturer's tensile and compression coupon test data.
- **New flexural elements rely on thin composite laminates to sustain bending strains > 1.5%** and for which the nonlinear behavior of the reinforcing fibers is significant.
- **Accurate prediction of strain/stress states** of these flexural elements **and their failure modes necessary** for HSC structures with improved packaging efficiency and deployed performance.
- **The traditional flexural testing methods for beams, i.e. 3-point and 4-point bending, are not suitable for thin flexures** as the large elastic deformations prior to failure cannot be accommodated.
- Important to **measure the laminate flexural rigidity over the operational strain regime of the material and the lifespan on the structure**, and from this, assess the behavior of the HSC structure during the stow-relax-deploy-recover operational cycle.
- Therefore, **need of new testing methods that allow large deformations under realistic loading and boundary conditions to measure nonlinearities in the moment-curvature relationship at large strains over long periods of time.**
- Need **viscoelastic models of textile thin-ply composites under high strains for predictive simulations of HSC structures.**

Data from Sandford, Biskner, Murphey, AIAA 2010-2698

Background & Motivation

- Previous tests developed for understanding the behavior of HSC flexures have limitations.
- **Simple Vertical Test** with tape hinges is prone to gravity-induced lateral loads and moments that tend to produce coupon/tape shear distortion at large rotation angles or induced curvatures.
- **Platen Test** generates a small localized region of high curvature in coupon apex, well away from coupon ends, that result in uncharacteristically high failure curvatures. The moment and stress over the coupon is highly non-uniform requiring complex structural analyses to interpret test results.
 - Used for determining upper limit on maximum coupon curvature or for **computing strains and stresses at failure**.
 - **Not used to assess bending stiffness** as it does not represent well the pure bending states of most HSC structures.
- **Large Deformation Four-Point Bending (LD-FPB)** subjects the coupon to a pure bending stress state, and used to measure bending stiffness including fiber nonlinear effects.
 - However, the **abrupt transition from flat to curved causes premature failure at test grips** (stress concentration).
 - Hence, **not normally used for bending strength and strain to failure evaluation**.

Collaborative Research Effort

Langley Research Center (LaRC)

- Large deformation bending test method development for thin composite flexures
 - Test coupon geometry and fabrication
 - Test fixture geometry and material
 - Test procedure and data capturing
- Flat coupon bending tests to failure
- Flat coupon bending relaxation
- Boom adhesive viscoelastic characterization
- Bending test method development for booms (in progress)

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University of Central Florida (UCF)

- Viscoelastic material modeling
 - Textile thin-ply composite elastic material modeling
 - Matrix viscoelastic modeling
 - Textile thin-ply composite viscoelastic material modeling (time-dependent behavior)
 - Repeatability/validation of flat coupon test data (same coupon batch but tested in different lab)
 - Boom adhesive viscoelastic material modeling
- Boom viscoelastic modeling and characterization (in progress)

Column Bending Test (CBT)

- CBT method initially developed by Thomas Murphey (Opterus R&D) and evaluated and refined for very thin composite flexures at LaRC: Fernandez, Murphey, AIAA 2018-0942.
- Test setup consists of double-symmetric, weight-balanced rigid fixtures arms pinned inside a clevis, which firmly clamp the specimen at an offset distance from the pin axis.
- As the fixture move vertically towards each other applying a compression force, they rotate causing a bending moment in the coupon.
- Combines best features of previous tests:
 - Vertical setup (as in Simple Vertical Test) **compatible with uniaxial load frames.**
 - **Generates a max stress state at the coupon center** (as in platen test) but only decreasing it to 80-90% of the max at the grips (and not 0%).
 - Because a larger volume of material is subjected to high stress, the **results are more representative of pure bending stress than in platen test.**
 - Stress state is mostly uniform (as in LD-FPB test), allowing **simple kinematic analysis** to estimate moment and curvature: **constant curvature assumption.**
 - Since curvature is slightly reduced at grips, **failure likely to occur in coupon apex** (as opposed to LD-FPB) for tests seeking bending strength/ failure strain.

CBT Kinematics: numerically calculating r and ϕ

- $\frac{\delta}{s} = 1 - \frac{2}{\phi} \sin \frac{\phi}{2} + 2 \frac{l}{s} (\cos \theta - \cos (\theta + \frac{\phi}{2}))$
- $\kappa = \frac{\phi}{s}$
- $\frac{r}{s} = \frac{1}{\phi} (1 - \cos \frac{\phi}{2}) + \frac{l}{s} \sin (\theta + \frac{\phi}{2})$
- $M_{max} = Pr$
- $M_{min} = Pl \sin (\theta + \frac{\phi}{2})$

CBT Initial Evaluation

- First rigorous evaluation of test method assumptions, mechanics and simplified kinematic equations.
- High temperature SLA 3D printed CBT fixture.
- 9-ply UD CFRP (MR60H/PMT-F7) coupon, 0.36 mm thick.
- **The constant curvature assumed is κ_x and the moment applied is M_x . Assuming $\kappa_y = 0$, the max moment at the coupon midgauge, M_{max} , is used to calculate D_{11} by linear regression on moving 10 data point windows of test results (slope of M- κ curve).**

For $\kappa_y \ll 0$

$$M_x = D_{11}\kappa_x$$

M- κ and D_{11} - κ curves for MR60H/PMT-F7 [0]₉

Measured angle of rotation of the lower and upper fixture arms, $\phi/2$, during a test.

Predicted vs measured angle of rotation of the fixture arm, $\phi/2$, during a test.

Surface axial strain, ϵ_{11} , at both sides of coupon

Failure strain in C according to manufacturer datasheet

Thin-Ply Materials & Laminates

Thin-ply lamina material properties

Material (fiber/resin)	Spread-tow Fabric Form	Width (mm)	FAW (g/m ²)	Ply AW (g/m ²)	FVF (%)	Cured Ply Thickness (μm)	E ₁ (GPa)	E ₂ (GPa)	ν ₁₂	G ₁₂ (GPa)	Vendor (fiber / resin)
MR60H/PMT-F7	UD	50	38.0	63.4	56	40 ± 3	174.4	8.4	0.259	6.4	Sakai Ovex / Patz M&T
M30S/PMT-F7	PW	1000	61.0	89.7	54	60 ± 3	94.2	94.2	0.026	3.9	Sakai Ovex/ PatzM&T

Thin-ply laminates studied

Label	Laminate	# Coupons tested	Avg thickness (μm)
M30S PW_45_x4	[±45PW] ₄	4	250 ± 10
M30S PW_0_x4	[0-90PW] ₄	4	250 ± 10
LAM1_0_x6	[±45PW ₂ /0UD ₂ /±45PW ₂]	5	330 ± 10

LAM1_0_x6

CBT Fixture: 3D Printed Plastic vs Titanium

- The same 0.3-mm-thick isotropic stainless steel sample was CBT tested at low strains at increasing temperature to assess time-dependent response of two additive manufactured fixtures made from SLA and Ti.
- Test data with high temperature SLA fixture showed relaxation at temperatures ≥ 50 °C well below the heat deflection temperature of the plastic material.
- Since load data with Ti fixture did show relaxation it was determined that the difference was due to the viscoelastic behavior of the plastic fixture at high temperatures. Conclusion: SLA not valid for accelerated relaxation/creep tests.

3D printed Titanium fixture

SS material softens with temperature (not relaxation)

3D printed SLA fixture

CBT Test Procedure for Viscoelastic Characterization

Test parameters adopted in this study

Temperature	40, 60, 80, 100, 120°C
Temp. steady state time	1.5 h
Fold/unfold rate	12 mm/min
Fold/unfold time	2 min
Estimated surface strain	1%
Relaxation time:	6 h
Recovery Time	2 h
Total test time	48 h

DIC tension-side strains during folding at temperatures 40°C - 120°C

DIC tension side strains at 40°C-120°C for 4-ply 45° M30S PW

Bending Relaxation Characterization Method

- CBT Bending relaxation tests of 4-ply 45° M30S PW laminate performed at 40°C -120 in 20 °C increments.
- Bending relaxation data shifted to form a master curve at 40 °C (max stowage temp.) using Time-Temperature-Superposition Principle.
- High degree of linearity of log of time shift factor vs temperature curve indicates that material behaves like a thermorheological one allowing the TTSP to be used for accelerated relaxation testing.
- In reality the CBT fixture does not restrict coupon transverse curvature ($\kappa_2 \neq 0$) during bending so the output data of the relaxation part is not the normalized $D_{11}(t)$ stiffness but $(\frac{M_1(t)}{\kappa_1 \Delta l})$ with κ_1 being constant. However, the latter will be referred as pseudo $D^*_{11}(t)$.

Long-Term Bending Relaxation For $\pm 45^\circ$ M30S PW

- Prony Series Fitting to experimental and simulated bending relaxation master curves at 40 °C. Prony terms can be used to validate/update finite element model (FEM) under development.
- 9-term Prony fit of the pseudo stiffness ($D_{11}^*(t) = \frac{M_1(t)}{\kappa_1 \Delta l}$) terms shown below for one $\pm 45^\circ$ M30S PW sample.
- The long-term coefficient ($D_{11,\infty}^*$) is similar for the test and FEM fit.
- Shifted test data allows to evaluate material response 2 years out, which is the max. required stowage requirement for boom application. The FEM can predict past the 2 year mark.

Prony series coefficients $D_{11}^* = D_{11,\infty}^* + \sum_{k=1}^n D_{11,k}^* e^{-\frac{t}{\rho_k}}$

9-term Experimental data fit			9-term FEM Numerical model fit		
k	ρ_k (s)	$D_{11,k}^*$ (Nmm)	k	ρ_k (s)	$D_{11,k}^*$ (Nmm)
∞	---	46.4701	∞	--	48.3955
1	0.04	0.1179	1	1.89E+01	0.6081
2	0.05	0.0032	2	1.00E+02	0.8042
3	49.40	4.4409E-14	3	1.00E+03	0.8195
4	441.02	3.8166E-08	4	2.00E+04	0.7250
5	2.58E+03	1.1046	5	1.00E+05	0.4394
6	4.64E+04	0.9509	6	1.95E+06	0.4431
7	7.67E+05	0.9736	7	1.77E+07	0.5439
8	9.09E+06	0.7079	8	1.74E+08	2.4962
9	1.0000E+08	1.1508	9	1.38E+09	0.0308

Normalized Bending Relaxation Master Curves

- Bending relaxation data for all samples was normalized by the thickness of the thicker coupon in each batch.
- The sample-to-sample thickness variability is acceptable and results show low standard deviations with LAM1 data having the largest spread given the large effect of the central 0° UD ply thickness on the laminate D^*_{11} value and its higher variability.
- $\pm 45^\circ$ PW laminate shows the most relaxation, followed by the LAM1 0° oriented laminate due to the viscoelastic matrix of the surface plies being highly loaded in shear as coupon gets bent axially.
- 0° PW laminate relaxes the least due to elastic fibers oriented in the principal loading 1-direction.
- The $\pm 45^\circ$ PW laminate showed the largest shift factors resulting in higher relaxation times, while the others had similar length predictions.

Micromechanics Modeling Method Overview

Unidirectional Tow/Ply Analysis

Unit cell model for a unidirectional tow/ply

Simulation carried in two steps:

Step 1: Apply axial strain of 0.1%

Step 2: Hold strain for 10E14 s.

Kirchhoff viscoelastic plate stress-strain relation:

$$\bar{\sigma}_i(t) = \int_0^t C_{ij}(t - \tau) \frac{d\bar{\epsilon}_j(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau$$

Relaxation stiffness matrix (transversely isotropic)

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} \end{bmatrix}$$

All entries modeled with Prony series of the form:

$$C_{ij} = C_{ij,\infty} + \sum_{k=1}^n C_{ij,k} e^{-t/\rho_k}$$

Unidirectional Tow/Ply Analysis

- Time dependence of C_{11} term is insignificant due to elastic fibers are dominant in the 1-direction.
- The rest of the tensor modulus terms show a similar time-dependence behavior due to the viscoelastic matrix response.
- Non-linear curve fitting using the least square method of the relaxation data from the numerical analysis was employed to obtain the Prony series coefficients.

M30S fiber tow relaxation moduli

Prony coefficients and relaxation time of tow fiber model

k	ρ_k	$C_{11,k}$	$C_{21,k}$	$C_{22,k}$	$C_{23,k}$	$C_{44,k}$	$C_{55,k}$
∞	–	183114.7	374.9	1131.8	269.4	135.3	207.2
1	1.89E+01	142.3	163.8	406.8	188.8	98.6	113.5
2	1.00E+02	209.0	241.5	600.8	277.2	140.0	161.8
3	1.00E+03	232.7	274.8	705.6	306.9	163.8	195.6
4	2.00E+04	138.0	163.2	414.1	180.5	95.6	114.0
5	1.00E+05	173.1	206.2	544.7	228.4	122.2	148.9
6	1.95E+06	113.9	137.1	356.5	146.2	79.7	97.9
7	1.77E+07	80.2	95.9	248.6	105.3	56.5	68.6
8	1.74E+08	355.8	429.8	1143.9	460.2	251.4	312.4
9	1.38E+09	373.0	461.3	1262.1	469.5	266.9	343.0
10	1.00E+10	383.6	482.0	1370.9	471.0	276.7	368.8
11	1.00E+11	412.3	527.2	1533.9	474.6	297.9	407.9
12	1.00E+12	398.0	515.1	1586.2	452.2	291.9	415.8
13	1.00E+13	495.3	657.6	2084.7	462.9	358.8	532.0
14	1.00E+14	56.1	76.7	290.8	48.1	42.6	69.6

Laminate Time-Dependent Analysis

Unit cell model for a 4-ply plain-weave laminate

Fiber tows use engineering constants derived from previous homogenization step

Kirchhoff viscoelastic plate equations:

$$N_i(t) = \int_0^t A_{ij}(t-\tau) \frac{d\epsilon_j}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^t B_{ij}(t-\tau) \frac{d\kappa_j}{d\tau} d\tau$$

$$M_i(t) = \int_0^t B_{ij}(t-\tau) \frac{d\epsilon_j}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^t D_{ij}(t-\tau) \frac{d\kappa_j}{d\tau} d\tau$$

Relaxation ABD stiffness matrix

All entries represented with Prony series of the form:

$$A_{ij} = A_{ij,\infty} + \sum_{k=1}^n A_{ij,k} e^{-t/\rho_k}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_6 \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{61} & A_{62} & A_{66} & B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{21} & B_{61} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{62} & D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{61} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{61} & D_{62} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_6 \\ \kappa_1 \\ \kappa_2 \\ \kappa_6 \end{Bmatrix}$$

Elastic Properties of M30S PW material

Moment-curvature response for the 3-ply 0° PW coupon

Strain

Stress

ABD matrix for the constitutive PW ply

$$ABD = \begin{bmatrix} 11900 & 467 & 0 & 0 & 2 & -1 \\ 467 & 11900 & 0 & 0 & 21 & 5 \\ 0 & 0 & 745 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ -3 & 1 & 0 & 28 & 1 & -10 \\ 1 & 41 & 0 & 1 & 28 & -10 \\ 10 & -10 & 4 & 0 & 0 & 16 \end{bmatrix}$$

B matrix terms are non-zero due to chosen in-phase (asymmetric) arrangement of PW textile tows

Strain

Stress

D_{11} [Nmm]	3-Ply Plain-weave M30S/PMT-F7
Single Unit Cell	28.0
Five Unit Cell	28.6

$$D_{11} = D_{22} = 28 \text{ Nmm}$$

CBT Bending Relaxation Data vs Simulation for 4-ply M30S PW

- Moment-curvature relaxation response at 30° C for the 4-ply M30S PW coupons tested was ultimately compared with the FEM simulation results.
- The 0° oriented samples showed a smaller relaxation than the 45° oriented ones but with a larger disparity between the computed and experimental results.
- Simulations with a laminate fiber volume fraction (FVF) between the two extreme test samples measured was used to establish an upper/lower bound. Lower FVF simulations results agreed more with experimental data.

Computed Axial Relaxation of 4-Ply M30S PW

Terms of the Extensional Stiffness Matrix, A

- Fiber-dominated directions (axial A_{11} , transverse A_{22}) are less prone to relaxation than resin-dominated directions (axial-transverse coupling A_{12} , shear A_{33}).
- All in-plane (A) relaxation moduli show small relaxation.

Computed Bending Relaxation of 4-Ply M30S PW

Terms of the Bending Stiffness Matrix, D

- Fiber-dominated bending directions (D_{11} , D_{22}) are more prone to relaxation/creep than bending coupling loading terms (D_{12}) or twist (D_{33}).

- All out-of-plane (D) relaxation moduli show slightly larger relaxation in 45° PW coupons but not as much as anticipated.

Conclusions

- It has been demonstrated that the proposed Column Bending Test (CBT) is an adequate method to study the long-term large deformation bending relaxation response of thin composite flexures.
- Iterative studies developed the CBT test procedure and test fixture design. Weight-balanced symmetric metal fixtures are recommended.
- The thin-ply composite laminates studied behaved like thermorheologically simple materials and the TTSP could be employed to predict from short-term relaxation tests at higher temperatures, the material's long-term response at a lower reference temperature.
- A 4-ply plain weave (PW) laminate and one that combines PW surface plies with central unidirectional plies ($[\pm 45PW_2/0UD_2/\pm 45PW_2]$) was studied in two different orientations by developing a two-step homogenization technique at different scales to evaluate the spread-tow textile composite material's relaxation ABD matrix. Computed and test results and Prony coefficients fits were compared.
- $\pm 45^\circ$ PW laminates showed the most relaxation, followed by the $[\pm 45PW_2/0UD_2/\pm 45PW_2]$ laminates due to the viscoelastic matrix of the surface plies being highly loaded in shear as coupons get bent. $\pm 45^\circ$ PW tests showed the largest disparity (10-15%) with computed data.
- 0-90° PW laminates relaxed the least due to elastic fibers oriented in the principal loading direction. Computed results matched tests well.
- PW simulations with a laminate fiber volume fraction (FVF) between the two extreme test samples measured was used to establish a upper/lower bound of the computed results. Lower FVF (53%) simulations results agreed more with experimental test data.

BACK-UP

Bending Stiffness/Strength Analysis

- Direct output from CBT is moment versus curvature (M- κ curve), which is related by coupon flexural rigidity, D_{11} .
- The constant curvature (κ) assumed is κ_x and the moment applied is M_x . The max moment at the coupon midgauge, M_{max} , is used to calculate D_{11} .
- D_{11} is computed by performing linear regressions on moving 5-10 data point windows of the test results (slope of M- κ curve).

$$M_x = D_{11}\kappa_x$$

$$D = \frac{\partial M_{max}}{\partial \kappa}$$

Tensile failure mode with brush-like fibers observed on thin UD coupons with some compression fibers intact.

M- κ and D_{11} - κ curves for 9-ply MR60H/PMT-F7 $[0]_n$ unidirectional laminate.

Surface Strains Analysis

- DIC systems used to measure full-field strain on at least one of the two sides of the laminate that was random speckled patterned for DIC tracking.
- Ultimately the average major strain, ϵ_{11} , values measured at the midgauge section were compared with those computed with CLT at the same region ($M_x = M_{max}$) under the simplifying assumption of constant curvature throughout the coupon ($\kappa_x = \kappa$) and linear material model.
- Given nonlinear rotational kinematics of CBT approach, the strain-vs-time curve is not linear. However, the strain-vs-curvature curves were fairly linear throughout the test, particularly for C side.
- For CUNI_IM_x9 the avg surface strain at failure at the coupon apex were 2% and 1.75% for the C and T sides, with coupons failing in tension. Tensile failure strain of 1.75% is expected (manufacturer data) but should fail at 1% in C.
- Tensioned fibers were able to stabilize compressed fibers past their expected failure strain up to a point where tensioned ones abruptly fail. Localized transverse and shear stiffness increment of C side fibers in bending.

$$\epsilon = \frac{\kappa t}{2}$$

Surface axial strain, ϵ_{11} , at both sides of a $[0]_9$ MR60H / PMT-F7 coupon vs test time.

Surface axial strain, ϵ_{11} , at both sides of a $[0]_9$ MR60H / PMT-F7 coupon vs curvature, κ .

Fixture Arm Rotation Angle Analysis

- Side view camera recorded video of lower CBT fixture arm as test progressed, which had a flag with a random speckled pattern to be used by the DIC photogrammetry system for rotation angle tracking.
- Video footage was transformed to still pictures at a specific rate and processed in VIC 2D to obtain accurate representation of fixture arm rotation involved, $\phi/2$.
- Comparison of angle data measured and CBT numerically computed showed that simple nonlinear kinematic equations of motion with coupon constant curvature assumption represent well the CBT test. Under this assumption, the slope of the (linear) $\phi/2$ -vs- κ curve is constant and equal to half the coupon gage length ($s/2$).
- Angle difference was less than 3 deg throughout the test for all coupons evaluated.

$$\kappa = \frac{\phi}{s}$$

Numerically computed vs measured angle of rotation of the fixture arm, $\phi/2$, during a $[0_c]_9$ test vs test time (left) and coupon curvature (right).

Bending Coupons Fabrication

- Panels are fabricated inside autoclave but following the same cure profile as the booms:
 - vacuum pressure (14 psi) and temperature (350°F).
- Top and bottom caul plates are used for more uniform thickness and smooth surfaces.
- Thin panels are sandwiched between G10 sheets for precision cutting into rectangular coupons
- Coupons are finally painted white and black speckled patterned to get full-field strain data (DIC)

Computed Relaxation Matrix of 4-Ply 0° M30S PW

- Fiber-dominated directions (axial A_{11} , transverse A_{22}) are less prone to relaxation/creep than resin-dominated directions (axial-transverse coupling A_{12} , shear A_{33}).

Terms of the Extensional Stiffness Matrix, A

- Fiber-dominated bending directions (D_{11} , D_{22}) are more prone to relaxation/creep than bending coupling loading terms (D_{12}) or twist (D_{33}).

Terms of the Bending Stiffness Matrix, D

Computed Relaxation Matrix of 4-Ply 45° M30S PW

- All in-plane (A) relaxation moduli show small relaxation
- All out-of-plane (D) relaxation moduli show larger relaxation

Terms of the Extensional Stiffness Matrix, A

Terms of the Bending Stiffness Matrix, D

